

DMart: Stellar Growth

Atul Kumar¹, Vinaydeep Brar² & A. B. Dadas³

ABSTRACT

DMart is India's most successful retailer. It has managed to post phenomenal growth across financial and operating parameters. DMart's strategy to ramp up its operations and offer cheaper merchandise has worked well. The company has grown its retail stores from 62 in FY13 to 176 in FY19. The revenues have grown by 33% during FY 15-19 and net profit has grown by 45% during the same period. DMart has managed to take advantage of under penetration of organized retail in India. It is a classic case of managing superior operational and financial growth.

Keywords: Retailing, Stores, FMCG, Organized retail

INTRODUCTION

DMart was started by Mr. Radhakishan Damani and his family to address the developing requirements of the Indian family. From the launch of its first store in Powai in 2002, DMart today has a grounded presence in 176 areas across Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Telangana, Chhattisgarh, NCR, Tamil Nadu, Punjab, and Rajasthan. With mission to be the lowest price retailer in the districts it works, the business keeps on developing with new areas in more urban communities.

The grocery store chain of DMart stores is owned by Avenue Supermarts Ltd. (ASL). The organization is headquartered in Mumbai.

¹ Dr. Atul Kumar is Professor with Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune. He can be contacted at atul.kumar@dpu.edu.in.

² Dr. Vinaydeep Brar is Professor with SNG Institute of Management & Research, Pune. He can be contacted at vinaydeep1983@gmail.com.

³ Dr. A. B. Dadas is Director with Neville Wadia Institute of Management Studies & Research, Pune. He can be contacted at drdadas.10@gmail.com.

WIDE SET OF OFFERINGS

- 1) Food: dairy, staples, groceries, snacks, processed foods, beverages, fruits, and vegetables
- 2) FMCG: personal care, home care, toiletries
- 3) General merchandise: garments, bed and bath, plastic goods

Figure 1: DMart Product Offerings

Source: Investor Presentation, FY19

STORES GROWTH

- 1) The company started its operations in 2003 with a single store in Mumbai.
- 2) It has ramped up its activity with a lot of new stores across India.
- 3) At the end of 2003, it had 62 stores, which expanded to 155 stores by 2018 and 176 stores by 2019.
- 4) This translates into a CAGR of 19% during FY13-19.
- 5) Maharashtra (70 stores), Gujarat (34) and Karnataka (16) are the key states for the company.

Figure 2: DMart Stores Growth

Source: Investor Presentation, FY19

OPERATING PARAMETERS

- 1) DMart's growth is driven by strong underlying operating data.
- 2) The billing count has increased from 6.7 cr. in FY15 to 17.2 cr. in FY19 (a CAGR of 27%).
- 3) The retail area has grown from 2.7 mn sqft. in FY15 to 5.9 mn sqft. in FY19 (a CAGR of 22%).
- 4) The stores reported same store growth of about 18-20%.
- 5) The revenues per sq ft have grown from INR 26K in FY15 to INR 35K in FY19 (a CAGR of 8%).

Figure 3: DMart Operational Data

Source: Investor Presentation, FY19

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

- 1) DMart has been able to clock very robust financial performance. This is underpinned by strong operating performance as explained above.
- 2) Revenues have increased from INR 6,434 cr. in FY15 to INR 19,916 cr. in FY19 (CAGR of 33%)
- 3) EBITDA has grown from INR 454 cr. in FY15 to INR 1,642 cr. in FY19 (CAGR of 38%)
- 4) EBITDA margins have expanded from 7.1% in FY15 to 8.2% in FY19
- 5) PAT has increased from INR 211 cr. in FY15 to INR 936 cr. in FY19 (CAGR of 45%).
- 6) Net profit margins have expanded from 3.3% in FY15 to 4.7% in FY19.
- 7) Net cash flow from operations has increased from INR 297 cr. in FY15 to INR 1,153 cr. in FY19.

Figure 4: DMart Financial Data

Source: Investor Presentation, FY19

CONCLUSION

DMart, operator of retail stores has managed to deliver outstanding performance. The company's revenues have grown at a CAGR of 33% during FY15-19 and net profit has grown at a CAGR of 45% during the same period. This stellar performance is driven by an equally strong operating performance. The retail area has grown by a CAGR of 22% during FY15-19. This is in turn driven by growth in number of stores (from 62 in FY13 to 176 in FY19). Thus, DMart is a great example of successful retail operations.

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